

A Survey Report on "Covid-19 Pandemic & Its effect on Students

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Abstract - The Covid-19 pandemic has brought about unprecedented changes in the lives of people worldwide. Among the most affected are students, this survey report explores the impact of Covid-19 on students and how it has affected their academic and social lives. To understand the effect of COVID-19 on students and the kind of changes that has occurred due to the pandemic, We conducted a survey amongst students of different age groups. A set of 13 crucial questions were asked to identify the behavioral changes and mental problems faced by the students during and after COVID-19. The survey was conducted in web based mode with questions based on student's mental health, their daily lifestyles, behavioral changes and the post pandemic choices and changes.

Keywords - COVID-19; Education, Student, Effect, Mental, Pandemic, Quality.

1.0 Introduction

The development of a nation is solely depended on its education system; it acts as a key element for developing the mindset of a particular individual. A developed mind is the source of ideas and innovations which will latter become the building blocks of a nation. "Health is Wealth"- we all have came across this term, cause at the end of the day all a person wishes is a good health. So, we can say a healthy poor person is richer than a person who has an unhealthy body.

The year 2019-2022 the world witnessed COVID-19 pandemic also known as a corona virus disease. It originated in China in December 2019. The first case was observed in Wuhan City in China and after that, it spread in the province of and all over China. Right in the blink of an eye it spread to all other parts of the world.

The WHO suddenly had to declare a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) On 30 January 2020 and after that when this epidemic was transferred in mostly all countries, WHO announced COVID-19 as pandemic on 12 March 2020. Most of the government of all nations had decided to temporarily close all schools, colleges and universities to diminish the spreading of

COVID-19. Educational institutions cannot maintain social distancing and therefore to minimize the skyrocket spreading rates the decision of temporary closure of Educational institutions was taken.

The spreading rate of COVID 19 was high in children as compared to adults. In India as per the following Lockdown rules, all institutions were closed from nursery level to postgraduate level leading to a serious drop in the quality of education. According to the UNESCO report, over 290 million students across 29 countries were affected. On that scenario physical teaching was shifted to online platforms.

But with online education came challenges like internet connection failure, disturbances in home environment, etc. Many students were not able to focus properly in that online medium of study. Many e-learning platforms were used like- zoom, Google classroom, etc but a huge gap was observed in between the students and education . Now we can state that crisis not only teaches us how to fight the situation but also how to shape our future.

2.0 Objective

Due to the constant disruptions faced during online classes, there came vast changes in students daily lives which in fact effected their everyday thinking and due to all these problems , a major amount of students were seen to have changed their habits , the effects of which are prominent now , when the pandemic is over and everything is setting back to normal.

The objective of this survey was to study these effects of COVID-19 pandemic on students of all age groups. The survey was administered using google forms platform, which requires an email id to participate in the survey, multiple entries from an individual account was restricted to ensure the collection of accurate data. The distribution of the question was made by the means of social media platforms, e-mail and standard messaging services. Clear instructions with google form were provided to ensure that the participant must be a student.

The survey has questions based on student's choices during COVID-19 pandemic, their daily lifestyles, their overview on online examinations etc

2.0.1 Survey Design

A web-based survey was conducted for the students through the medium of Google Forms from March 4 to March 16, 2023.

The questions asked were based on :

- (a) The general information of the participants such as age, name, residence, class, gender, etc.
- (b) Information about their daily online learning outcomes, mainly the effects that online education had on their day to day life.
- (c) Their social interactions and dependencies during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.
- (d) Their health due to the change in lifestyle during and after the pandemic, we also included further questions about stress which affected the mental health of the students, child parent relationship, etc.

3.1 Characteristics of the participants:-

A total of 13 questions were set to be asked in the survey for which a total of 134 responses was recorded from students. Out of The 134 participants 67.2% were male participants and 32.8 % were female participants. The minimum age of a participant was recorded to have been 13 and the maximum age was recorded to have been 31.

91% out of the 134 participants resided in the State of West Bengal.

The maximum number of responses came from students aged 20 years at the time of the survey. Students aged 19 and 21 were the 2nd and 3rd highest number of participants. The fact to be noted is that more than 80% or 85.07% (to be precise) number of students who took part in this survey lie in between the ages 18 and 22.

The most number of students who responded to the questions in the survey were enrolled in undergraduate courses with students from 1st year undergraduate studies accounting for the maximum amount participation.

3.2 Responses and Their Analysis:-

I. Our patience level during and after COVID-19 pandemic

Fig.1 Pie Chart depicting the percentage of responses recorded for the question asked.

- Objective of the question :

The question was asked to identify behavioral changes that occurred in students due to COVID-19 pandemic.

- Analysis of the responses :

From Fig.1 it can be noted that the maximum number of students (53) who took part in the survey experienced a decrease in their patience levels due to COVID-19 pandemic. From the rest of the participants, 49 participants experienced an increase in patience level and 32 participants had no effect on their patience level.

From the above data it can be concluded that most of the student's patience has been affected due to COVID-19. Number of students who were negatively affected is slightly more than the number of students who had positive effects.

II. Due to COVID-19 pandemic what kind of changes came in our daily life

Fig.2 Pie Chart for calculating responses about what kind of changes came to daily life due to COVID-19 pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question was asked to identify the amount of changes in our daily lifestyle that occurred in students due to COVID-19 pandemic.

- Analysis of the responses :

From Fig.2 it can be noted that the maximum number of students (54%)72 out of 134 who took part in the survey experienced huge amount of changes in their daily lifestyle due to COVID-19 pandemic. 34% of the participants (46) experienced little changes and 10% participants (14) have not experienced change in their daily lifestyles.

From the above data it is clear the daily lifestyle of students has certainly been affected. Number of students who were experienced huge changes dominates over those who experienced little to no changes which mean generally students in a whole have experienced huge changes in their daily lifestyle.

III. Quality of education due to COVID-19 pandemic

Fig.3 Pie Chart for calculating responses about student view on the quality of education that they Received during or after COVID-19 pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question was asked to find out student's view about the changes in the quality of education due to the pandemic.

- Analysis of the responses :

From Fig.3 it is to be noted that the maximum number of students (88% or 118) feel that the quality of education that they received during or after the pandemic has decreased as compared to the pre pandemic era education. 7% of the students feel that there has been no change in quality of education that they receive and 5% students believe that the quality of education has increased.

From the above data it is clear that students who are the core part of the education have not received good quality education during and after the pandemic. The shift towards online education during the pandemic can be accounted for this drastic change but it needs to be studied

IV. How much we connected socially during/ after COVID-19 pandemic situation

Fig.4 Pie Chart for calculating the effects on student's social connection due to COVID-19 Pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question was asked to identify the effects on student's social connectedness due to the pandemic.

- Analysis of the responses :

From Fig.3 it is to be noted that 32% of students experienced an increase in their social connections .29% of the students feel that they had lost the habit to stay connected to people totally. 19% report that everything was normal as before and another 19% report to have experience reduction in their social connections and only 1% of student feel something else about their social connections.

The fact to note is that most of the students reported to have experienced changes in their social connections.

As studies have shown that social connectedness of a person do affect their well being we can conclude from the above data that a students who had maintained the same amount or experienced an increase in social connection had experienced increased or no effects on their social life. But the rest of the students who had experienced less social interactions or lost the habit to connect with people totally had experienced changes in their social lives. From the above data it is clear that the social connectedness in students was affected with a part of student experiencing increased social interactions or same amount of interaction and another part having lost the habit to stay connected or having experienced reduction in connectivity.

V. During COVID-19 pandemic our mental condition

Fig.5 Pie Chart to analyze the effects on mental condition due to COVID-19 Pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question was asked to analyze the effects on student's mental condition due to the pandemic.

- Analysis of the responses :

From Fig.3 it is to be noted that 48% of student's mental condition deteriorated due to COVID-19 and 27% of the students had anxiety issues due to COVID-19. 18% report that their mental condition had not changed and only 6% of participants have observed improvement in their mental conditions.

From the above data it can be concluded that student's mental health has been negatively affected with the maximum number of students having experienced deterioration in their mental conditions and many students having experiencing anxiety related problems.

VI. In the last 2 years how much has our tolerance level changed

Fig.6 Pie Chart to analyze the changes in tolerance level due to COVID-19 Pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question is related to mentality of the students where we want to know about the changes in tolerance level. Here, we are using the word tolerance level as the ability of a person to handle mental pressure.

- Analysis of the responses :

From the above data 43 out of 134 participants responded to have experienced increase in tolerance level. 39 participants experienced quick tiredness. 28 participants loss the interest of hearing and understanding and 19 participants have responded to a decrease in their tolerance level with only 5 having no changes.

The negatively affected students again amount to be the maximum in this case also with a total of 86 participants (39 participants who experienced quick tiredness +28 participants who lost the interest of hearing and understanding +19 participants who responded to a decrease in their tolerance level).

So, it is again clear that COVID-19 did have negative effects on student's tolerance levels.

VII. Mentality Development due to pandemic.

Fig.7 Pie Chart to record the mentality development in students due to COVID-19 pandemic.

- Objective of the question :

This question is related to mentality of the students where we want to know about their mindset development.

- Analysis of the responses :

43 out of 134 participants responded to have experienced loss of confidence. 31 participants experienced depression. 43 participants had calm and polite mindset and 12 participants had confident mindset with 7 having other things to say about.

Just Like the previous question, students who have been negatively affected dominated the students who had positive development. A total of 74 participants had their mindset development negatively affected.

VIII. In the online examination, books/notebooks/google search/guardian support to answer any question has been provided or observed

Fig.8 Pie Chart to understand external help received by students during online examination.

- Objective of the question :

This question is related to find out students habits during online examination.

- Analysis of the responses :

63 out of 134 participants responded to have taken partial help from other sourced during their examination. 36 participants took full help to give their examinations. 33 participants had not used any external sources to answer their questions and 2 having other things to say about

As it was noted by many academicians, it can be concluded that the online examination system was not a suitable way of conducting exams as it's clear from the above data that external help was used by students which as per the guidelines of examinations held throughout India is not tolerable.

IX. Due to COVID-19 the relationship between parents and children have

Fig.9 Pie chart for understanding parent child relationship during COVID-19.

- Objective of the question :
This question is related to find out the effects in student's and their parents relationship.

- Analysis of the responses :
57 out of 134 participants responded that they had no change in their relationship with parents. 55 participants confirm that their relationship with parents became stronger. 11 participants having deterioration in their relationship and 10 having a strained relationship with their parents with only 1 participant having something else to say. Participants had good relationship with their parents which mean that, the pandemic had positive effects on parent child relationship.

X. When schools or colleges first reopened after lock-down, student interest to attend school or college was

Fig.10 Pie chart for the data collected after post pandemic school reopening.

- Objectives of the question:

This question was asked to understand student's feeling when educational institutes reopened after lockdown.

- Analysis Of the questions:

Most students were excited or very excited due to the reopening of school (42 and 39 respectively). 16 students were demotivated, 12 students irritated and 15 had lack of confidence. From the above data it is clear that most of the students were eager to again continue with their offline classes.

XI. Expecting online examination after regular physical classes observed

Fig.11 Pie chart for identifying student's expectations related to post pandemic examinations.

- Objectives of the question:

This question was asked to understand student's expectations related to post pandemic examinations

- Analysis Of the questions:

45 students were not expecting online exams, 29 students were expecting online exams, 29 students were partially biased about the matter and 29 students were not able to manage their online exams.

So, from the above data it is clear that students were confused about the mode of examination after reopening.

XII. Facing difficulties in the understanding of class topics , managing home-works due to uncovererd topics of previous years(because of online classes).

Fig.12 Pie chart for identifying the amount of difficulties that students had to face in their studies.

- Objectives of the question:

This question was asked to identify the difficulties that students had to face in their studies.

- Analysis Of the questions:

Most students had faced little to very much difficulty in their daily academic activities (42 and 38 respectively).24 students report that they are still facing difficulties .13% students out of 134 had initially faced difficulties.

From the above data it is clear that the students had to face or are still facing difficulties in their daily academia and it will take time to recover from it.

XIII. What are the kind of demands expected by the students post COVID-19 crisis

Fig.13 Pie chart for identifying the students expectation in the post pandemic era

- Objectives of the question:

This question is a multiple choice based question was asked to understand the demands that students expected to get fulfilled in the post COVID era.

- Analysis Of the questions:

Students were expecting that they will go out somewhere with their friend or family which clearly reflects that students wanted to socially connect. Many wanted to go out of station and to go out with friends which.

Most of the students selected options which included going out or travelling to places which clearly shows the tendency among student to not be confined in their homes anymore.

4.0 Limitations:

As this survey was conducted in a digital mode it included voluntary participation which made it difficult to record sufficient amount of responses to record data.

5.0 Conclusion:

In this study, the findings indicate that COVID-19 basically had more negative effects on student's lives than positive effects. With significant impact on mental health, behavior, thinking process and mentality development COVID-19 has left a vast effect on students and youth which directly or indirectly still affects them. The post pandemic situation has returned a certain level of normality but disruptions are still common and it will take some time to fix these issues

5.0 References

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